

AFLATOXIN DETECTION USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNIQUES: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

Mycotoxins are secondary metabolites that threaten the food and feed industries, in which aflatoxins are the most common and toxic of all mycotoxins. Aflatoxins can contaminate crop products at any stage – before cultivation, on the field, during transportation, storage, or processing period. It has become a global concern affecting the health of man and animals and the economy. There are several popular methods for determining and quantifying aflatoxin. However, early detection of this pollutant is critical for feed and food safety and human well-being. Traditional methods of aflatoxin detection though effective, often require expensive equipment and expertise, making them less accessible in resource-limited settings. This paper explores the growing role of artificial intelligence (AI) in enhancing aflatoxin detection. Artificial intelligence (AI) techniques, including machine learning (ML) algorithms, computer vision, and spectral imaging, offer more accurate, efficient, and affordable detection methods. Therefore, this review discusses some of the traditional methods of detecting aflatoxin and explores the prospective opportunity of using artificial intelligence to detect food and feed. It further discusses some challenges and recommends using ongoing AI techniques. This review concludes that advancement in AI-driven detection technologies, collaboration and capacity building will strengthening aflatoxin analysis and ensuring food and feed safety.

Keywords: Aflatoxin, Artificial intelligence, *Aspergillus flavus*, Detection, Food Safety

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Mycotoxins are toxins that occur naturally through certain fungi (mould) which grow in feed or foodstuffs (Khan et al., 2024). Its effects on the health of such feed/food are adverse, from acute poisoning to long-

term impacts such as immune deficiency and cancer (Mafe and Büsselberg, 2024; Zahir et al., 2024). They are regular and common metabolites, and their negative impacts on human and animal health have been a source of worry (Ilesanmi et al., 2024).

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Evidence shows that mycotoxins have immunosuppressive, mutagenic, carcinogenic, hepatotoxic, nephrotoxic, and toxic characteristics (Dan-Ologe et al., 2026; Ilesanmi et al., 2025). Mycotoxins contaminate crops at any stage of food production, starting with choosing seeds for cultivation, cultivation practices, harvesting, transportation, proper storage, and processing (Zhang et al., 2024). Nuts, cereals, fruit, chocolate, spices, oil seeds, coffee, and many more food/feed crops are frequently contaminated (Agriopoulou et al., 2020).

Aflatoxins, ochratoxins, zearalenone, fumonisins, trichothecenes (deoxynivalenol [DON], and T-2 toxin) are the major classes of mycotoxins (Awuchi et al., 2021). Mycotoxins are toxins that occur naturally through certain fungi (mould) which grow in feed or foodstuffs. Its effects on the health of such feed/food are adverse, from acute poisoning to long-term impacts such as immune deficiency and cancer (Dan-Ologe et al., 2026). Various fungal species can produce each of these toxins, the most harmful being (mycotoxins), the aflatoxin, often created by *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus* (Ilesanmi et al., 2024). These species grow in soil, decaying plants, hay, and grains and are widespread in warm, humid climates.

People and animals frequently ingest aflatoxins from contaminated food products because of their great thermal stability, which conventional heat treatments cannot eliminate. Many countries' Food and Drug Administrations have created regulatory criteria and residue levels for the most common and hazardous toxic substances (mycotoxins) in food and drugs to protect both living organisms from the danger of toxic organic pollutants. Because these mycotoxins threaten the public's health, it is critical to detect their presence in the food chain as soon as possible (Adeyeye and Yidiz, 2016). Managing aflatoxin contamination is a global challenge, especially in a warm and humid environment that encourages these fungi's growth (Sulyok et al., 2015). Traditional methods for aflatoxin detection, such as chromatographic techniques and immunoassays, often require expensive equipment, trained personnel, and lengthy processing times, making them less accessible in low-resource settings (Kumar et al., 2021).

Recent advances in artificial intelligence (AI) have created new opportunities to improve aflatoxin detection methods. Aflatoxin detection could be revolutionised by AI-driven methods that use computer vision and machine learning (ML) algorithms to provide quicker, more accurate, and more affordable results (Inglis et al., 2024). These methods significantly increase the effectiveness of

food safety monitoring systems by analyzing large, complicated datasets, finding trends, and predicting aflatoxin levels in different samples. Aflatoxin detection accuracy can be maintained or increased with the integration of AI, which can also help researchers gain deeper insights into the data and provide a significant advantage over traditional lab analysis in terms of efficiency, cost, and scalability (Gao et al., 2021).

However, while AI has enormous potential in aflatoxin detection, some problems remain. The reliability of AI models is strongly dependent on the quality and diversity of the data used for training, and there is frequently a paucity of standardised, large-scale datasets for aflatoxins detection. Furthermore, implementing AI-driven solutions in real-world scenarios faces challenges such as high initial costs, technical competence needs, and data privacy and security concerns.

Therefore, this review highlights some improvements and advances in technologies used to identify and quantify the aflatoxins in agricultural products. We further discuss the performance, prospects, and challenges of some ongoing Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques for detecting aflatoxin in agricultural products.

An overview on Aflatoxin

Aflatoxin is a metabolite created by *Aspergillus spp*, notably *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus parasiticus*, and *Aspergillus nomius*, in environments that promote optimal fungal development at 36 to 38°C and above 85% humidity (Wagacha et al., 2008; Ilesanmi et al., 2023). Crops can become infected by the fungi that produce aflatoxin in the field, at harvest, during storage, and during the processing phase (Kumar et al., 2021). The toxic effect of the substance can manifest immediately or long-term, contingent upon the degree of exposure experienced by the organism. According to Dhakal (2024) the impact of these substances can result in teratogenic, mutagenic, carcinogenic, or immune suppressive effects. Additionally, they are hepatotoxic to both animals and humans. According to (Kowalska et al., 2017), aflatoxins have been found to impact significant human body organs, particularly the liver and kidneys. Additionally, there have been reports of aflatoxins affecting the reproductive organs (Jalili et al., 2024; Ye et al., 2024). The acceptable levels of aflatoxins in foods and feeds are determined and recommended by agencies responsible for the Food and Drug Administration in every country, which has the authority to recall any food or animal feed with higher levels of aflatoxins than the established acceptable limits.

Aflatoxins display fluorescence under UV light, though they are seen to be colourless to pale yellow crystals. The solubility of these substances in water is limited, ranging from 10-20 μ g/ml. However, they exhibit higher solubility in polar solvents, such as chloroform, menthol, and dimethyl sulfoxide (Vankayalapati, 2018)..

2.1 Types of Aflatoxin

Aflatoxin B₁, Aflatoxin B₂, Aflatoxin G₁, and Aflatoxin G₂ are the most prevalent and toxic aflatoxins out of the over eighteen distinct types found (Kumar et al., 2017). Milk from dairy cows nourished with feed contaminated with aflatoxins has been shown to contain the aflatoxins M1 and M2. The prevalent types of Aflatoxin are discussed below:

2.1.1 Aflatoxin B₁ (C₁₇H₁₂O₆)

The most potent mycotoxins produced by *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus*, aflatoxin B₁ (See Figure 1), is found to be hepatotoxic, hepatocarcinogenic, mutagenic and teratogenic (Kumar et al., 2021). It accumulates throughout the development of many crops and is converted into (aflatoxin M₁).

Figure 1: The chemical structure (3D) of Aflatoxin B₁. (Source: NCBI, 2024)

2.1.2 Aflatoxin B₂ (C₁₇H₁₄O₆)

Aflatoxin B₂ (see Figure 2), which is synthesised by *Aspergillus flavus* and *parasiticus*, is a mycotoxin that exhibits moderate potency in terms of its hepatotoxic, hepatocarcinogenic, mutagenic, and teratogenic properties (Kumar et al., 2021). It is commonly detected in various crops, albeit in limited quantities compared to AFB₁. Additionally, it undergoes metabolism to AFM₂.

Figure 2: The chemical structure (3D) of Aflatoxin B₂. (Source: NCBI, 2024).

2.1.3 Aflatoxin G₁ (C₁₇H₁₂O₇)

According to Singh et al. (2022), Aflatoxin G₁ (Figure 3) is a highly potent mycotoxin that exhibits carcinogenic and genotoxic properties produced by *Aspergillus parasiticus*. The formation of this substance occurs during the developmental stages of various crops such as peanuts, corn, cereals, and oilseeds. The substance exhibits comparable structural and toxicological characteristics to aflatoxin B₁.

Figure 3: The chemical structure (3D) of Aflatoxin G₁. (Source: NCBI, 2024).

2.1.4 Aflatoxin G₂ (C₁₇H₁₄O₇)

Aspergillus parasiticus and other strains of *Aspergillus parasiticus* have been found to produce the Aflatoxin G₂ (Figure 4) toxin, as reported by Singh et al. (2022). It can be found in many foods, including legumes, oil seeds, spices, fruits, etc. It is derivative of aflatoxin G₁.

Figure 4: The chemical structure (3D) of Aflatoxin G2. (Source: NCBI, 2024).

2.1.5 Aflatoxin M1 (C₁₇H₁₂O₇)

Aflatoxin M1 (Figure 5), despite being synthesized in small amounts by *Aspergillus spp.*, is linked to the development of chronic liver damage and cancer (Ramadan and Al-Ameri, (2022)). The level of toxicity is comparatively lower than that of aflatoxin B1. Aflatoxin M1 is observed in dairy animal cheese and milk sourced from animal's ingested feed or food contaminated with the AFB1 toxin. Its presence has been detected in the livers, kidneys, blood, faeces, and urine of animals that consume contaminated food. AFM1 is a metabolite of aflatoxin B1.

Figure 5: The chemical structure (3D) of Aflatoxin M1. (NCBI, 2024).

2.1.6 Aflatoxin M2

Aspergillus flavus and *parasiticus* produce Aflatoxin M2 (Figure 6), albeit in small quantities. Consuming contaminated food by dairy animals is a known factor that leads to the production of AFM1. Hence, AFM2 is known for dairy products. The bodily fluids and excretions of the affected animals, including their livers, kidneys, blood, faeces, urine, and milk, have been identified as potential sources of the substance

(Ramadan and Al-Ameri, (2022)). This substance can be classified as a derivative of aflatoxin B2.

Figure 6: The chemical structure (3D) of Aflatoxin M2. (Source: NCBI, 2024).

The impact and significant role of aflatoxin in the food and feed industries

The economic impact of aflatoxin in the food and feed sectors is noticed in a decrease in the amount and quality of goods that are available for sale, the refusal of food by the global market, and the expenses incurred due to animal illness and death (PACA, 2012). The capacity of aflatoxins to pollute both human food and animal feeds has emerged as a significant apprehension within the feed industries. According to a report by WHO in 2018, aflatoxins have been found to contaminate many crops worldwide. This contamination has led to the destruction of up to twenty-five percent of food crops globally, resulting in substantial economic losses in developed and under-developed nations (Fedlu et al., 2019). Contaminated food products are the gateway to animal and human exposure to agents of aflatoxicosis such as meat (Ilesanmi et al., 2025; Dan-Ologe et al., 2026), dairy products or eggs (Jiang et al., 2021; Syraji et al., 2025). Maize and groundnut, consumed in significant quantities in developing nations, are the primary feeds vulnerable to contamination (Tembo et al., 2023; Syraji et al., 2025), with contaminated feeds impacting animal husbandry productivity negatively (Jiang et al., 2021; Popescu et al., 2022). Prenatal exposure to aflatoxins through the consumption of contaminated products by expectant mothers may have detrimental impacts on the foetus, and infants may be affected via breast milk (Jiang et al., 2021, Syraji et al., 2025). Although data on the mortality rates is available, it may be challenging to ascertain the mortal cases in developing countries. According to Syraji et al. (2025), a significant proportion of the population in developing countries, exceeding 5 billion citizens, may be exposed to aflatoxin by consuming contaminated food.

Based on the impacts on the industries, several scientific and regulatory authorities, for example, the International Cancer Research Institute, have a set tolerable standard limits for aflatoxin at 20 ppb in 4.0 grain and 0.5 ppb in milk in the United States while 4 ppb in foods in some European countries (Yu et al., 2023). European Union (EU) standards of aflatoxin B₁ and total aflatoxin in foods are 5 and 10 µg/kg, respectively (Herzallah, 2009) with 0.05µg/kg (50 ppt) in milk, and 25 ppt for baby food (Cucci et al., 2007). The Codex Alimentarius Commission (Codex), together with the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)/World Health Organization (WHO), have set tolerable limits for 15 µg/kg total aflatoxins in feedstuffs, which also prescribes a maximum limit of 0.5 µg/kg for aflatoxin M₁ in milk (Yun et al., 2015). This is to reduce or control aflatoxin ingestion and its circulation to the communities. This has made many countries establish regulations to limit exposure depending on the usage though many developing countries do not adhere to them. Adherence to regulations depends on factors such as the cost of analyzing or testing and the loss of the crops when aflatoxins are finally discovered in contaminated crops. The food and feed industries face economic losses due to the rejection of their contaminated products, especially in the international market. The losses can result from the forced reduced price, rejection at the distribution channel, or diversion to nonhuman or even non-fee uses, all because of the inability of the products to meet the aflatoxin standards.

3.1 Subsection(s)

3.1.1 Subsubsections

Different Methods of aflatoxins detection

There are numerous ways to identify aflatoxins in food and feed for various purposes, and numerous techniques for their detection and analysis have been thoroughly studied to create those that are extremely specific, practical, and helpful (Abbas, 2021).

Several methods of detecting aflatoxin has been engaged overtime through analytical and immunological methods (Abbas, 2021). Every methods discovered always come with modifications which may be minor sometimes, mainly from the existing basic methods for specific food commodities. The variations could be in the extraction solvents used to extract the mycotoxins from various food matrixes and in the analytical techniques used to evaluate the fluorescence strength of the mycotoxins under study. Various approaches are available for various purposes, starting with basic fast test kits, progressing to regulatory control techniques in official laboratories, spectroscopic methods, and chromatographic methods (Table 1). A number of techniques for detecting aflatoxins in food and feed have been thoroughly studied in order to create highly specific, practical, and useful methods. These techniques are available for a variety of purposes (Abbas, 2021).

Table 1: Evaluation of different methods for analysis of aflatoxins in food and feed

Method	Sample preparation	LOD	Field Applicable	Reference
AgraStrip®	Simple extraction with Methanol	4 ppb	Appropriate	Romer Labs Division Holding.
Immunodipstick	Extraction only	5 µg/Kg	Appropriate	Luppa et al., 2001.
CHARM EZ-M	Water based extraction	1 ppb	Inappropriate	Charm Sciences.
Fluorometer	IAC	5–5000 µg/Kg	Inappropriate	Malone et al., 2000.
TLC densitometer	Liquid Extraction, SPE	1–20 ng/kg	Inappropriate	Balzer et al., 1978; Park et al., 1994.
HPTLC	Liquid Extraction	Pictogram	Inappropriate	Liang et al., 1996.
RIA	Liquid Extraction	1 µg/Kg	Inappropriate	Sun and Chu 1979.
FTIR	Liquid Extraction	<10 µg/Kg	Inappropriate	Pearson et al., 2001.
ELISA	Liquid Extraction	1 µg/Kg	Inappropriate	(Omar 2020)
HPLC	IAC or SPE	0.5 µg/Kg	Inappropriate	(Rahmani et al., 2009)
LC-MS	Liquid Extraction	0.1 µg/Kg	Inappropriate	(Kokkonen et al., 2005)

Method	Sample preparation	LOD	Field Applicable	Reference
QCMs	Liquid Extraction	0.01–10 ng/mL	Inappropriate	(Gaag et al., 2003)
SPRS	Liquid Extraction	3.0–98 ng/mL	Inappropriate	(Yu et al., 2012)
Electrochemical	Liquid Extraction	0.1–2 µg/Kg	Inappropriate	(Masoomi et al., 2013; Linting et al., 2012)

TLC - Thin Layer Chromatography; HPTLC - High-performance Thin Layer Chromatography; RIA – radioimmunoassay; FTIR - Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy; ELISA - Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay; HPLC - High-Performance Liquid Chromatography; LC-MS - Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry; QCMs - Quartz Crystal Microbalances; SPRS - Surface Plasmon resonance Spectroscopy (Source Abbas, 2021).

5.0 Traditional and cultural methods of detecting aflatoxins in food

Traditional techniques for identifying aflatoxins in food that are frequently based on cultural customs include visual inspection, taste, and smell testing, as well as the use of blacklight (ultraviolet light) to detect fluorescence (Abbas et al., 2008; Liu et al., 2022). More accurate and dependable detection is provided by contemporary scientific techniques including ELISA, biosensors, and chromatography (TLC, HPLC, LC-MS). Aflatoxin detection in food is often accomplished through sensory assessments, physical inspections, and quite straightforward chemical testing, according to traditional and cultural methods (Rahi et al., 2019). These methods are known to be more affordable and easily accessible. Numerous validated techniques exist for the identification of Aflatoxin contamination in agricultural crops. These can be cultural or analytical methods as presented by the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC). Here are a few such traditional and cultural techniques that are employed:

5.1 Cultural methods

Mycotoxin detection using cultural methods is based on first the sense organs like visualization, smelling and through smell. Aflatoxin-induced bitter or off-flavor in food can also serve as a preliminary indicator, and farmers and food handlers frequently employ visual indicators, such as mold development or discoloration, to identify possible contamination (Adeola & Babalola, 2025). Scientifically, it can be based on the fluorescence of the mycotoxins produced

by the sample or the visible colour of pigments the colonies produce (Khan et al., 2024). These methods generally analyze extracts prepared from the samples and provide the identification and quantity of mycotoxins even at a low ppb (ng/g) range (Abbas et al., 2004; Sudini et al., 2015). Cultural methods have several advantages that include the following:

- It is affordable.
- It is easy to handle.
- The major equipment for the method is available even in developing countries.
- Its assessment is well-defined.

Cultural methods also have several disadvantages including the following:

- The assessment is not specific to the mycotoxin type.
- Positive assessments may be quantitative concerning the amount of fungus in the sample, but the amount of mycotoxin present will not necessarily correlate with the infestation level.
- The sensitivity is very low compared to the analytical methods.
- There is high variation in the detection limits, accuracy, requirements, and applications.

5.1.1 Blue Fluorescence

Cultural method can be employed to note the difference between toxigenic and non-toxigenic strains of *Aspergillus species* (Chen et al., 2024). Identification of *Aspergillus species* from sample feed may be achieved through a blue, fluorescent technique to determine a qualitative cultural method (Rajarajan et al., 2021). This method can be implemented using either solid or liquid media. The principle of this method rests on the ability of aflatoxins to emit a blue fluorescence upon exposure to UV light. Aflatoxin-producing isolates are observed to have grey or black colonies in the UV photographs, while the nonproducing isolates are observed to have white colonies (El-Dawy et al., 2024). The absorption of UV light is primarily attributed to Aflatoxins B₁ and G₁.

5.1.2 Yellow Pigmentation

In this instance, yellow pigmentation (YP) was observed, predominantly on the ventral surfaces of the

colonies. According to (Gupta and Gopal, 2002) findings, the production of yellow pigment cannot be considered a dependable indicator for determining the quantity of aflatoxin present in all types of media. The utilization of ultraviolet photography presents a potential avenue for expedited identification of isolates that produce aflatoxin. However, the method is limiting as it does not differentiate between the different aflatoxins (A1 and B1). Additionally, it does not provide specific aflatoxin concentrations in samples, and this may be possible only using analytical methods.

5.2 Analytical methods

Over time, various analytical techniques have demonstrated efficacy in detecting aflatoxin in feed and food samples. According to (Abbas et al., 2004), analytical methods have several advantages that including the following:

- They are sensitive.
- They are reliable.
- They are quantitative.
- They are specific to the mycotoxin type.
- They can analyze multiples of mycotoxins.
- They are definitive.
- The analysis results are accepted in the international market.

Analytical methods also have several disadvantages including the following:

- It is expensive to purchase and maintain.
- It requires skilled technical know-how.
- The methods are time-consuming.
- There are waste disposal problems because of the required solvent extraction needed for the methods.

The analytical methods are discussed as follows:

5.2.1 Chromatography

Chromatography is a molecular identification methodology that employs a chromatographic technique to provide unparalleled sensitivities. This method is recognized as a viable approach for the analysis of aflatoxins and is based on the physical interaction between a mobile phase and a stationary phase (Narayanan & Reddy, 2023). Typically, the mobile phase is a liquid or solid that permeates through or along the fixed bed. Nowadays, liquid, gas, and supercritical fluids are employed as mobile phases, and the names of chromatographic procedures come from the characteristics of the mobile phase. According to (Vosough et al., 2010), chromatography is the predominant quantitative technique employed in

research and routine aflatoxins analysis. The sorbent, which is a partition between the solid and liquid stationary phases, is put as a spot on the stationary phase after the sample to be examined has been dissolved in the mobile phase (Wacoo et al., 2014). Various chromatography techniques can be employed; examples include:

- a. Gas chromatography (GC),
- b. Liquid chromatography Mass Spectroscopy (LCMS),
- c. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and
- d. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) (Sulyok et al., 2015).

a. Gas chromatography (GC)

Gas chromatography (GC) is predominantly employed for analyzing non-volatile, small groups of biological molecules, as noted by (Roux et al., 2010). Most mycotoxins are non-volatile, so this analytical technique is commonly utilized for their detection and quantification. Gas chromatography (GC) employs a carrier gas as the mobile phase and a stationary phase consisting of a liquid coating on inert solid particles within a lengthy stainless steel or glass column (Abbas, 2021). Higher affinity components of the sample mixture for the stationary phase flow more slowly through the column, whereas lower affinity components move through the column less obstructed. In addition, each sample component should have a unique partition coefficient that determines how quickly it passes through the column (Boyer, 1993). Following separation, the volatile compounds are detected using a mass spectrometer (MS) and either an electron capture detector (ECD) or a flame ionization detector (FID) (Pascale, 2009). Derivatization may be necessary for aflatoxins to be detected due to their nonvolatility (Scott, 1995). Some of the disadvantages of GC are listed below:

- Inability to retain the memory of prior analyses,
 - Drifting responses,
 - Inconsistent calibration curves, and
- Variability in repeated analyses (Pettersen and Langseth, 2002).

Gas Chromatography

Figure 7: Gas Chromatography (Source: Aryal, 2024)

b. Liquid chromatography Mass Spectroscopy (LCMS)

Using and exploiting liquid chromatography-mass spectroscopy (LCMS) for mycotoxin analysis, particularly aflatoxin, has become increasingly common and advanced (Abbas, 2021; Petterson and Langseth, 2002). According to Deng et al. (2017) and Zhang and Xu (2019) the technique has advantageous traits such as excellent resolution, lack of restrictions on sample purification during extraction, high sensitivity, and applicability to various edible

vegetable oils. The technique is a distinctive approach for detecting aflatoxin, which provides exceptional precision in measurement, a wide range of detection, accurate identification, and the ability to analyze multiple mycotoxins in a single analysis. Additionally, the method employs soft ionization conditions that enable access to the molecular mass of intact biological molecules (Alejandro et al., 2011; Di Stefano et al., 2012). LCSM disadvantages include the prolonged pre-treatment phase, expensive purchase, and the necessity for proficient operators (Abbas, 2021).

Figure 8: Liquid chromatography Mass Spectroscopy (LCMS) (Source: Rama et al., 2024)

c. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)

A notable degree of precision, sensitivity, and automation characterizes the use of the HPLC technique for detecting aflatoxins. Aflatoxin detection in foods and feeds is commonly achieved through various techniques, among which the two-phase approach (standard and reverse phase) is widely employed. Additional methods include UV absorption, fluorescence detection, mass spectrometry, and amperometric detectors (Alejandro et al., 2011). HPLC technique is a quantitative methodology that is well-suited for the purification of sample extracts in an online capacity and has the

potential to be integrated with various detectors (Li et al., 2006). According to Herzallah (2009), HPLC is a rapid and dependable analytical technique that yields precise and trustworthy outcomes for aflatoxin detection in a relatively brief period. HPLC has developed low detection limits and uses a small amount of sample to produce structural information (PACA, 2012). However, HPLC is an expensive technology that should only be operated by skilled professionals. Additionally, this limits its application to well-equipped laboratory settings exclusively, not field settings.

High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)

Figure 9: High Performance Liquid Chromatography (Source: Aryal, 2024).

d. Thin layer chromatography (TLC)

Aflatoxin identification in food and feed samples, even at low quantities, is frequently done using this technique. This method has been officially recognized as the preferred approach by the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC) since 1990, according to Abbas (2021). TLC can identify various categories of mycotoxins in a solitary examination and possesses high sensitivity for example, see Figure 7. Furthermore, the cost of this method is comparatively

lower than that of HPLC, and it is a straightforward technique (Gilbert and Anklam, 2002). The capability to perform repetitive detection and quantification, as reported by Sherma (2000) and Fuchs et al. (2010), is achieved without any phase interference. One limitation of this approach is that it necessitates the involvement of extensively trained experts and is also susceptible to imprecision due to sample application, plate development, and interpretation inaccuracies.

Thin Layer Chromatography

Figure 10: Thin Layer Chromatography

(Source: Aryal, 2024).

Figure 11: Detecting aflatoxins through thin-layer chromatography. (The figure shows blue dots representing the position of aflatoxins on the TLC plate (Ismail et al., 2024))

5.2.2 Immunological Methods

Immunological methods relate to the specific interaction between antibodies and antigens to detect specific proteins in each sample. The methods were devised considering the distinctive and substantial binding interaction between antibodies and antigens (Yun et al., 2022). The formation of the antibody-antigen or receptor-ligand complexes can be measured spectrophotometrically by monitoring the change in photon absorbance of light energy. In other cases, the

binding events and the resulting complexes may need to be amplified for improved signal recognition, which has been accomplished using a variety of labels, including enzymes, fluorophores, and radioisotopes, among others. The formation of the antibody-antigen or receptor-ligand complexes can be measured spectrophotometrically by monitoring the change in photon absorbance of light energy. In other cases, the binding events and the resulting complexes may need to be amplified for improved signal recognition, which has been accomplished using a variety of labels, including enzymes, fluorophores, and radioisotopes, among others (Wacoo et al., 2014). In addition to conventional chromatographic techniques, immunochemical analysis methods have recently been

used to identify mycotoxins. Commonly employed techniques in immunology include the following:

a. Radioimmunoassay (RIA)

The application of RIA is limited due to its dependence on the competitive binding of radiolabeled and non-radiolabeled antigens with accessible antibodies. Unmarked antigen engages in competitive binding with a predetermined quantity of antibodies against the radioactive antigen. The amount of radiolabeled antigens and antibodies is a known factor. In contrast, the number of non-labeled antigens is an unknown variable that exhibits an inverse relationship with the number of radiolabeled antigens. This method's limited application or usage is attributed to its capacity to process only a few samples and its high cost (Chu, 2004). The utilization of RIA has been observed in aflatoxins detection and assessment

(Wacoo et al., 2014). Aflatoxin levels in food samples have also been analyzed using radioimmunoassay. Other uses of radioimmunoassays include the qualitative and quantitative determination of aflatoxin B1 levels (Gupta and Gopal, 2002; Bennett, 2010) and aflatoxin M1 levels (Chen et al., 2021). The main benefit of radioimmunoassay is its capacity to conduct multiple analyses at once with high levels of sensitivity and specificity (Criseo et al., 2001). While the RIA can analyze numerous samples simultaneously, it necessitates using pure antigens, and the radioactive isotope employed in the process poses a significant risk and presents challenges in terms of disposal and storage. These challenges have limited the regular usage of RIA in the aflatoxins analysis. Other limitations of RIA include:

Figure 12: Radioimmunoassay (RIA) Procedure. (Image Source: Howell-Moroney, 2022).

- it requires an antigen in a pure state,
- a radioactive isotope is used as a label and is associated with potential health hazards, and
- it has problems associated with the storage and disposing of the low-level radioactive waste.

b. Enzyme-linked linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA)

Enzyme-linked linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) is a commonly utilized method in detecting aflatoxin (Horváth et al., 2022). The objective of this technique is to concentrate proteins from complex proteins in a given sample, relying on the principle of targeted immune reactions between antigens and antibodies. The methodology relies on an enzymatic colorimetric reaction, wherein the quantification or identification of

the analyzed substance is contingent on its concentration (Horváth et al., 2022). Enzyme-linked linked immunosorbent assay has undergone significant advancements and widespread adoption in various sectors such as food analysis, biotechnology, chemical analysis, clinical research, environmental studies, and other related industries. The present methodology is characterized by its distinct components, namely the reagent for chromogenic, substrate, enzyme label and element for immune recognition.

A noteworthy advancement in ELISA technology is the introduction of ELISA kits that facilitate the detection of aflatoxin in food and feed agricultural products (Akinniyi, 2025). For instance, Qi (2019) employed ELISA and ultra-performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (UPLC-MS/MS) techniques to identify the presence of

aflatoxin B1 (AFB1) in peanut oil. The detection limit was $1.08 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ which was higher than that of UPLC–MS/MS ($0.01 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). The developed kit exhibits a distinct capacity for recognition, is cost-effective, poses no risks to health, and can analyse multiple samples concurrently.

According to (Wu et al., 2019], the ELISA kit has certain disadvantages. For example, it is an expensive, time-consuming, and cumbersome procedure. Another drawback is the assay's dependence on the matrix, which is affected by the interaction of the matrix's components with the target antigen. However, the development of the nanomaterials-based ELISA (nano-ELISA) is to address its limitations with superior performance. Wu et al. (2019) continued that technological progress will lead to the emergence of promising applications of ELISA technology.

5.3 Biosensors for aflatoxins detection

A variety of nanomaterial-based biosensors are used to analyze and monitor aflatoxin-contaminated food products. Aflatoxin detection has been done using a variety of transducers that provide different types of analytical data, including current, potential, conductance, impedance, absorbance, and fluorescence (Odoemelam & Osu, 2009; Jia et al., 2020). The rate and occurrence of the analyte-receptor interaction are transformed into a measurable physical phenomenon via the transducer. Aflatoxin-detecting biosensors have been divided into groups according to the transducer (Odoemelam & Osu, 2009; Jia et al., 2020).

5.3.1 Electrochemical Biosensing

Electrodes are used in electrochemical biosensors to transform various analytical signals, such as voltage, current, and impedance. According to (Gurjeet et al., 2024), the electrochemical biosensor employed for AFB1 detection can generate diverse forms of analytical signals. This technique has garnered significant interest in evaluating food and feed quality due to its distinct advantages: exceptional capability, cost-effectiveness, expeditiousness, and sensitivity (Yin et al., 2022). The conventional techniques for transduction encompass amperometry, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), and voltammetry (potentiometry) (Shi et al., 2020).

5.3.2 Amperometric Biosensors

This is an electrochemical apparatus that exhibits sensitivity with the utilization of variations in the

measuring current as the analytical signal. This method of mycotoxin detection is purportedly flawless. The observed alteration in the current indicates a corresponding variation in the concentration of AFB1 in food samples. According to (Pundir et al., 2019), an amperometric biosensor comprises three electrodes and they are –

- Functional electrodes are made of gold, carbon, or platinum.
- Reference electrodes made of silver (Ag) or silver chloride (AgCl) have a fixed potential that controls the working electrode's potential.
- Auxiliary electrodes, which are used to measure current flow.

5.3.3 Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)

EIS demonstrates the capacity to monitor the changes in aflatoxins at the interface between electrode surface modifications and detect the presence of aflatoxins in agricultural products. During the analysis, the food or feed samples under investigation are coupled with a biometric element, which generates an electrochemical response characterized by changes in conductivity and capacitance, as detected by an impedance biosensor (Kim et al., 2019). The analysis findings are provided as changed electron flow on the working electrode (Lu et al., 2020). The simplicity of this detection method renders it applicable for detecting diverse agricultural products.

5.3.4 Voltammetry Biosensors

Voltammetric biosensors are made of functional, reference, and auxiliary electrodes (Pundir et al., 2019). These biosensors address the challenge of acquiring analytical data by utilizing ion-selective electrodes. Despite this approach's recognized accuracy, cost-effectiveness, speed, and sensitivity, its usability can be challenging, mainly when the current is unstable. The reason is that the accuracy of a voltammetric analysis is usually limited by the ability to correct for residual currents, particularly those due to charging. The circuit changes of functional and reference electrodes are used to detect mycotoxins in agricultural product samples (Kaur et al., 2023).

5.4 Fluorescence/Near Infrared Spectroscopy (FS)

This method utilizes the fluorescence colors generated by toxins when exposed to Ultraviolet (UV) light to identify the presence of specific types of aflatoxins. The technique described can detect aflatoxins in a

diverse range of agricultural products and food items (Wu et al., 2018; Yadav et al., 2021). Because of this feature, the approach stands out for being sensitive and specific in identifying mycotoxins and other elements (Karoui and Blecker, 2010); Ma et al., 2018). According to (Syraji et al., 2025), the fluorescence emission rate exhibited by the aflatoxin G toxin surpasses that of the aflatoxin B toxin.

5.4.1 Terahertz Spectroscopy

The ability of terahertz as a novel technology for non-destructive detection of mycotoxin has been demonstrated in recent studies (Afsah-Hejri et al., 2019; Rawson and Sunil, 2021). Optical and electronic technology makes it suitable for employment in research and industrial analysis (McIntosh et al., 2021). Terahertz is frequently employed in the feed mill or food industry due to its robust analysis capabilities, as noted by (Afsah-Hejri et al., 2019; Feng and Otani, 2021). While terahertz represents a non-destructive detection method for AFB1, its limited detection limit, restricted penetration depth, scattering effects, high cost, and inadequate database are among the challenges that must be addressed (Yin et al., 2022).

6.0 Blacklight test

This method is an expensive and temporally efficient approach that accurately detects negative samples of aflatoxins (Yao et al., 2023). This approach is frequently utilized in the context of animal nutrition. When observed under UV light, it provides optimal contrast in low-light conditions. The method's constraint lies in its provision of solely an initial confirmatory examination, lacking precision regarding the number of toxin levels to scrutinize. Moreover, samples that do not exhibit fluorescence properties are not required to undergo this technique. The limitation of this method is that the use of safety goggles is strongly advised when conducting the black light test due to potential health hazards to the eyes. This is because the eye fluorescence resulting from reflected long-wave UV radiation can produce a blue haze that may pose a risk to eye health (Alcaide-Molina et al., 2009).

7.0 Laser-Induced Fluorescence (LIF) screening method

The LIF screening technique has garnered attention because of its specificity, sensitivity in detection, and utilization of a laser light source wavelength (Yin et al., 2022). One of the benefits of this approach is its

expeditious implementation and its non-invasive nature in identifying AFB1 in various types of edible oils (Chen et al., 2021; He et al., 2022). The LIF method is subject to limitations that have impeded its widespread adoption and utilization. These limitations include the influence of extraneous variables like the precision and potency of the apparatus, ambient conditions of temperature, humidity, and the physicochemical parameters of the sample being detected (Yin et al., 2022).

8.0 Photomultipliers (PTM)

The employment of PTM is a customary practice during the initial phases of industrial operations, primarily to identify the presence of aflatoxin M1 in dairy livestock. This method can facilitate the assessment of the milk production process (Vas et al., 2020). The instrument exhibits high sensitivity, detecting measurements at the parts per trillion level and measuring signals with extremely low fluorescence levels. It is suited for measuring bioluminescence, chemiluminescence, or ultralow fluorescence. In addition, these devices are equipped with detachable emission and excitation filters, which enable the placement of the most appropriate emission filter to select the desired spectral region. According to Singh & Mehta, (2020) and Mishra et al. (2025), the PTM is a compact and portable sensor for quick detection of aflatoxin without pre-concentration of the sample, which enhances its efficacy in early detection.

9.0 Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

PCR is a molecular technique implemented as a potent means for detecting and characterizing mycotoxins (Meskini et al., 2026). This technique has surfaced as a contemporary approach for identifying aflatoxins in comestibles (Levin, 2012; Rodriguez et al., 2012). Various DNA-based detection techniques, including PCR, Nested PCR, Polymerase chain reaction-restriction fragment length polymorphism (PCR-RFLP), and Real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR), have been utilized for the identification of aflatoxigenic fungi due to their highly sensitive and specific nature. Hence, an optimized technique is required to detect and identify aflatoxigenic fungi in food and feedstuffs. This is necessary to assess and mitigate the potential health hazards linked with them. According to Degola et al. (2007), the PCR technique is deemed more precise and efficient when compared to alternative methods.

10.0 Spectrometry

Mass Spectrometry Multiple Reaction Monitoring (MRM) technology as an analytical approach for mass spectrometry detection has enhanced the dependability of both qualitative and quantitative outcomes (Wang et al., 2021).

11.0 Ion mobility spectrometry

Ion mobility spectrometry is a scientific method used for the purpose of characterizing chemicals by analyzing the velocity of gas-phase ions in an electric field. Miklós et al. (2020) recognized Ion mobility spectrometry as an alternative approach for detecting the concentration of aflatoxins in food and feed. This method is characterized by its low detection limit, rapid response, ease of use, portability, and affordability. According to Sheibani et al. (2008), its utilization renders it unfeasible to measure samples in a minute of 0.25 ng. Also, its limitation is that it malfunctions when it is overloaded. As a result, the device cannot be used for several hours.

12.0 Fourier Transform near Infrared (FT-NIR) spectrometry.

Fourier transform near infrared consists of measuring the absorbance of the sample to light whose wavelength varies in the range known as the Near Infrared (NIR) Bailly et al. (2024) reported that the utilization of FT-NIR to detect aflatoxins depends on the calibration requirements necessary to establish standard reference chemical processes. Fourier transform near infrared technique is recognized for its expeditious and uncomplicated operation, precision, non-invasive nature, and ability to forecast samples' chemical and physical properties through a solitary spectrum parameter enabling several components to be determined simultaneously based on multivariate calibrations (Kim et al., 2007; Bailly et al., 2024). It facilitates the simultaneous determination of multiple components by utilizing multivariate calibrations. Fourier transform near infrared analysis has a detection range (15 to 500 mg/kg) that is high compared to other chemical techniques such as high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and thin-layer chromatography (TLC).

Artificial Intelligence AI Techniques in the Detection Of Aflatoxin

A lot of technological advancement has brought about so many modern machines and gadgets capable of performing tasks, analyzing, and making decisions by programmed systems. Artificial intelligence (AI) is a

computer term impacting contemporary settings, forming a link between the physical and digital world. Many aflatoxin detection techniques have been developed and designed using computer intelligence to overcome the problems of early identification, species characterization, and scent simulation, among others. Through machine learning (ML) algorithms, deep learning frameworks, and sophisticated data analysis techniques, AI provides cutting-edge approaches for the swift and dependable identification of aflatoxins across diverse food matrices (Deshmukh et al., 2025). Some of these methods are discussed in the following sections:

1.0 Spectral Imaging and AI Integration

The integration of artificial intelligence with spectral imaging methodologies, including Near-Infrared (NIR), Hyperspectral Imaging (HSI), and Raman Spectroscopy, significantly improves the detection of aflatoxins. AI algorithms can analyze spectral data to discern absorption patterns or signatures linked to aflatoxins, even when present in minimal concentrations (Zhu et al., 2024).

1.1 Hyperspectral imaging

Hyperspectral imaging is a cutting-edge technology that offers immense potential for evaluating the quality of various food products. Combining imaging and spectroscopy enables the simultaneous capture of spatial and spectral information (Laborde et al., 2020; Rahman et al., 2020; Panda et al., 2021). One of the promising applications of hyperspectral imaging is the rapid and efficient screening of aflatoxin contamination in food and feed. Studies have demonstrated its effectiveness in detecting large-scale aflatoxins (Kabir et al., 2025; Mishra et al., 2022). Hyperspectral imaging is a method that leverages the spectral and spatial characteristics of an object. The dataset comprises numerous contiguous wavebands corresponding to each spatial position of the sample. The information gathered is commonly known as a hypercube, which is structured into a three-dimensional data cube (Chen et al., 2013; Manley, 2014). Hyperspectral imaging is founded on the principle that distinct patterns of electromagnetic energy reflection, scattering, absorption, and emission at specific wavelengths are exhibited by all biological materials. This is because of the variations in their chemical compositions and inherent physical structures (ElMasry et al., 2012). The distinctive attribute of an object known as a spectrum or spectral signature fingerprint is a widely recognized pattern.

Chu et al. (2017) investigated the potential of short-wave infrared (SWIR) hyperspectral imaging within the wavelength range of 1000–2500 nm and achieved an overall classification accuracy of 82.50%. Furthermore, (Han and Deng, 2019) introduced a pixel-level detection algorithm for aflatoxin utilizing deep learning techniques, analyzing UV–visible–NIR hyperspectral image cubes (292–865 nm) and had 95% accuracy for peanuts within the concentration range of 20–100 ppb. Previous research has established that hyperspectral imaging can successfully detect aflatoxin levels as low as 10 ppb (Kimuli et al., 2018).

Hyperspectral imaging presents significant advantages for assessing aflatoxin levels in individual kernels, primarily due to its pixel-level predictive capabilities (Mishra et al., 2021). Consequently, it is possible to utilize the spectral signature as a distinctive means of characterizing, distinguishing, and classifying various types or categories of a particular substance (ElMasry).

The "staring imager" setup and the "push-broom" or line scan system" are two techniques for creating hyperspectral images from a sample, as mentioned by (Gowen et al., 2007).

1. Staring Imager: This technology takes images progressively at various wavelengths while the image field of view remains stationary.

2. Push-Broom - Using this technique, when the sample moves about the instrument, spectral data can be simultaneously acquired from a series of nearby spatial positions.

Numerous studies have used NIR hyperspectral imaging to identify, detect, and distinguish mycotoxins in foods and feeds (Shahin and Symons, 2012; Yang et al., 2012; Karuppiyah et al., 2016; Zhang and Xu, 2019). Conversely, NIR hyperspectral imaging is constrained by the duration required for data pre-processing and classification, which is contingent upon factors such as sample size, image resolution, and the capabilities of computer hardware and software Cozzolino D. (2025). Furthermore, the lack of ascertained quantification of mycotoxins (Orinaa et al., 2017) represents an additional constraint.

1.2 Near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy

A near-infrared (NIR) is a non-destructive, quick, and economical analytical method for quality assurance and determining a product's molecular makeup (Hossain and Goto, 2014). By applying light in the near-infrared range to the sample, one can measure the absorption or reflection of light at various wavelengths. This measurement allows for the

identification of the presence and abundance of aflatoxins in the samples. The NIR approach was used to find mycotoxin contamination in food and feed. In the food, pharmaceutical, and agricultural sectors, this technique has become widely accepted for process monitoring, product quality control, and raw material testing (Teye et al., 2013; Tomuta et al., 2013). Mycotoxins in a variety of food products, including maize (Berardo et al., 2005), wheat kernels (Pettersson and Åberg, 2003), and rice (Dachoupakan et al., 2013), have been identified using this technique.

This technique has been developed to analyze the presence of mycotoxin contamination in food and agricultural goods. Hernández-Hierro et al. (2008) evaluated the application of NIRS transmittance instruments for the determination of mycotoxin. AFB1, ochratoxin A, and total aflatoxin in red paprika were all analyzed by NIRS measurement using a remote reflectance fiber-optic probe. According to Fernández-Ibañez et al. (2009) NIRS technology is an excellent substitute for quickly detecting AFB1 in wheat grains. Dachoupakan et al. (2019) reported that the NIR showed good predictive performance when it was used as a rapid method to detect aflatoxins in brown rice, suggesting that it could have practical applications as a fast method to detect aflatoxins. The electromagnetic spectrum is used in the near-infrared technique. The NIR technology measures the vibrations of the bonds between the atoms in organic compounds. The frequency of the vibrations matches a chemical bond in the substance under investigation (Manley, 2014). NIR spectroscopic instrument comprises a few parts, such as a radiant energy source, a wavelength selection device, a sample presentation mechanism, an energy converter that converts radiant energy into an electrical signal, and a signal processor and readout system (Oñate et al., 2024). The contribution of each part is dependent on the sample's chemical constitution and physical parameters.

1.3 Fourier transform infrared photoacoustic spectroscopy (FTIR-PAS)

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) is a method employed for the identification and analysis of the molecular structure of compounds. FTIR measures the amount of light absorbed at various wavelengths by the sample by exposing it to completely infrared light. It can analyse the entire spectrum at once using the Fourier Transform approach, which increases the analysis's speed and scalability. In contrast to measuring what is transmitted, this non-invasive technique allows for the direct assessment of energy absorption by a sample (Ryczkowski, 2010). Based on

the photoacoustic effect, the Photoacoustic Spectroscopy (PAS) method is used in Fourier transform mid-infrared (FTIR) systems. According to Ryczkowski (2010) and Sivakesava and Irudayaraj (2000), this effect is brought about by the interaction of a modulated infrared beam coming from the spectrophotometer with a sample surface that is housed inside a sealed cell and gassed with inert helium. The apparatus, according to Sivakesava and Irudayaraj (2000), has the capacity to carry out depth profiling, enabling non-invasive examination of underlying layers beneath the sample's surface. The effectiveness of this method has been examined and supported by numerous studies, including ones on food analysis (Irudayaraj et al., 2010), microorganism detection (Irudayaraj et al., 2002), classification of rapeseed varieties (Lu et al., 2014), analysis of potato chips Sivakesava and Irudayaraj (2000), pea seeds (Letzelter et al., 1995) and coffee (Gordillo-Delgado et al., 2012). The application of a diffuse reflectance mode of Fourier transform (FT) NIRS for detecting fumonisin B1 and fumonisin B2 in naturally contaminated ground maize was assessed (Gaspardo 2012).

1.4 Raman Spectroscopy

Raman Spectroscopy is a non-invasive analytical method that yields comprehensive insights into chemical structures, phases, polymorphism, crystallinity, and molecular interactions (Deng et al., 2022). This technique relies on the interaction between light and the chemical bonds present in a material. Its applications span various research domains, including medical biology, food safety, and electrochemistry (Han et al., 2020; Cui et al., 2020; Deng et al., 2022). The underlying principle of Raman spectroscopy is the polarizability of chemical bonds, which makes it particularly sensitive to the symmetrical vibrations of covalent bonds found in non-polar groups. Its insensitivity to water and reduced band overlap allow Raman spectroscopy to deliver more valuable qualitative and quantitative data regarding the chemical functional groups of mycotoxin compounds and their derivatives compared to traditional spectroscopic methods, thereby offering molecular-level insights into mycotoxins (Deng et al., 2022). Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of this technique for the rapid screening of mycotoxin-contaminated grains, oilseeds, and their derivatives (Golightly et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2009; Sohn et al., 2004).

Raman spectroscopy is a technique that involves the scattering of light by molecules when exposed to a

high-intensity laser source. Most scattered light retains the same wavelength as the incident laser, a phenomenon known as Rayleigh scattering, which does not yield significant analytical information. In contrast, a minute fraction of the scattered light—approximately 0.000001%—is dispersed at varying wavelengths, which are indicative of the chemical composition of the analyte; this is referred to as Raman scattering. This method is characterized by its rapid and non-destructive nature, eliminating the need for sample pre-treatment. Raman spectroscopy has found widespread application across various research domains, including the quantitative analysis of mycotoxins (Deng et al., 2022). For example, Yang et al. (2021) employed Raman spectroscopy to identify zearalenone (ZEN) and aflatoxin B1 in six maize samples exhibiting varying levels of mold contamination.

2.0 Colour imaging

Colour is an essential method in examining grains and cereals; it helps to differentiate between the varieties of grains based on colouration and discoloration because of damage (Genaeve et al., 2020). Colour images are described either using the primary colours red, green, and blue (RGB system) or by converting the RGB component value of the object image to the main factors of human colour sensation, namely hue, saturation, and intensity (HSI system) (Nisha et al., 2021).

Colour imaging has been used to identify and characterize mycotoxin contamination in several food sources, such as wheat, according to Zohrabi et al. (2024). Following (Wang et al., 2004), variations in the color of the impacted feed can be used to identify the fungus that creates mycotoxins. Similarly, Kim et al. (2023) reported using color imaging to screen for and identify mycotoxin contamination in maize. The procedure calls for the use of a digital camera to take the image, a stage to hold the sample safely, an image capture board or digitizer to make digitization easier, a light source to ensure proper lighting, and computer hardware and software to process the images efficiently (Vithu and Moses, 2016). The most common method for creating digital photographs uses a high-resolution CCD chip and the related gear (Patel et al., 2012). To enhance image quality or eliminate unnecessary causes of variation, pre-processing is done on the photographs of the object being studied (Vithu and Moses, 2016).

One potential limitation of this approach is the potential challenge faced by colour imaging in accurately identifying the classification of fungi

species. Additionally, the range of electromagnetic optical data that can be observed is restricted, and the sole source of variation may be physical discolouration in the kernels. Hence, it is plausible that this methodology may exhibit efficacy in a considerably progressed phase of the infection (Tallada et al., 2011).

3.0 Thermal imaging

The functioning of thermal imaging systems relies on detecting temperature variations between two entities, specifically an object and its background, and the subsequent transformation of this difference into a discernible image. The thermal imaging methodology involves the examination of dissimilarities in thermal characteristics between an aflatoxin-contaminated specimen and a non-contaminated one to conduct its analysis. According to Chelladurai et al. (2010), the biochemical changes brought on by fungal growth account for the difference in the rate of heating and cooling between contaminated and uncontaminated food crops. The benefit of thermal imaging devices is that they operate without requiring external light sources; these passive systems function effectively in both daylight and complete darkness. Also, the microprocessor and other electronic elements read data from the thermal sensor, process it, and create shapes in the display that represent a visual interpretation of the data. An observer then views this image through an eyepiece or directly on a screen. Thermal imaging devices may include integrated video recorders to capture pictures and videos of samples to be analysed, as well as various auxiliary features such as wireless data transmission (photo, video) to external devices via radio channels or Wi-Fi, remote control of the device using a mobile device, integration with a laser rangefinder (displaying rangefinder data on the unit's screen), and integration with GPS sensors (geopositioning features).

A drawback of this strategy was noted by Chelladurai et al. (2010), who observed that due to similarities in the chemical makeup of kernels, it is unable to distinguish between several species of fungi. Other restrictions include the chance that the heating and cooling process will hurt heat-sensitive items and the possibility of unwelcome fluctuation in the thermogram due to changes in heat distribution (Orinaa et al., 2017).

4.0 Deep Learning for Sensor Data Analysis

Artificial intelligence methodologies, particularly deep learning algorithms, are employed to interpret

data obtained from sensors designed to identify the presence of aflatoxins through their chemical or physical characteristics, such as electronic noses or tongues. These AI models can discern intricate patterns within sensor data, enabling them to distinguish between contaminated samples and those that are not. For instance, Autoencoders and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) have been used to examine data obtained from electronic sensors to detect aflatoxins in dairy and grain products.

4.1 Electronic nose

The technique has been developed to emulate olfaction to distinguish various scents (Machungo et al., 2023). The advancement of gas sensor array technology, commonly called an "electronic nose" (e-nose), holds significant potential as an analytical instrument. An e-nose comprises various nonspecific chemical sensors that detect volatile organic compounds (VOCs), generating a unique fingerprint for the substance under examination (Ottoboni et al., 2018). It functions as a signal collection unit. It utilizes digital software to convert the output from detecting odours into a format that is easily comprehensible (Liu 2012). The device has electronic chemical gas sensors that exhibit distinct selectivity for detecting various odours. The electronic olfactory system operates based on a non-discriminatory detector that engages with volatile materials in the sample's headspace. Following the interpretation of the sensor, artificial neural networks (ANN), discriminant analysis (DA), logistic regression (LR), and pattern recognition algorithms were used (Marco et al., 2021). The computer receives the signal from the sensor and utilizes calibration and training procedures to classify the signal, ultimately resulting in pattern recognition (Baldwin et al., 2011). The method exhibits certain drawbacks, such as its cost and the paucity of information regarding its efficacy in quantifying aflatoxin in agricultural products (Cheli et al., 2012).

In addition, these electronic noses are instrumental in evaluating the olfactory quality of various food products, including different types of vinegar (Wu et al., 2020), the freshness of meat (Chen et al., 2009), and the detection of meat spoilage (Kodogiannis, 2018).

Figure 13. Schematic diagram of a typical e-nose system (Kodogiannis, (2018))

4.2 Electronic tongue

E-tongue technology typically necessitates regular recalibration of the multisensory array (Shimizu et al., 2019). An e-tongue comprises a multisensory array that employs non-specific or low-selective sensing units, leveraging their cross-sensitivity to discern various liquid mediums, predominantly through electroanalytical techniques. This process often generates a substantial volume of data, which requires the application of multivariate statistical methods for both qualitative and quantitative analyses, thereby enhancing the visualization of information derived from both straightforward and intricate liquid samples (Shimizu et al., 2019).

Shimizu et al. (2019) reported that e-tongues represent a promising category of analytical instruments characterized by their straightforward operation, rapid response times, affordability, and seamless integration with various systems, including microfluidic and optical technologies. These features facilitate miniaturization and enhance sensitivity for measurements in complex liquid environments. Consequently, e-tongues offer a compelling alternative for tackling numerous challenges in environmental monitoring, particularly concerning emerging pollutants like heavy metals and toxins.

Figure 14. Schematic of a typical e-tongue system (Source: Tan and Xu, 2020)

5.0 Neutron tomography

Neutron transmission tomography provides high sensitivity and sufficient spatial resolution. Thus,

objects in the size of a few millimetres up to tens of centimetres can be scanned in reasonable time (Tremisn et al., 2021). This method is based on the phenomenon of absorption and scattering that a

neutron beam exhibits while passing through a particular substance. This technique for aflatoxin detection is used to observe the internal macroscopic configuration and material composition of the feed specimen, according to Lehmann et al., (2020). The distribution of attenuation coefficients within the sample volume is shown in a series of 2-D images used in the neutron tomographic approach to create a 3-D volume (Williams et al., 2025). As a result of neutrons' sensitivity to the detection of hydrogen, neutron tomography is frequently used in biological research to track water transport within samples (Trtik et al., 2021). The sample will be rotated at an angle to make it easier to examine structural changes in maize kernels that have been infected with *A. flavus* (Mannes et al., 2020). The neutron tomographic method is limited by its inability to extract precise information from the images and by its restricted access to the reactor facilities that control neutron production. The approach also has a reduced spatial resolution of roughly 10 to 50 μm (Mannes et al., 2020; Lehmann et al., 2020; Trtik et al., 2021).

6.0 X-ray micro-computed tomography

X-rays possess wavelengths that are capable of penetrating through matter. The resultant image can accurately depict the material's internal defects, contamination, and structural alterations (Ou et al., 2021). According to Albers (2024), the X-ray micro-computed tomography technique utilizes soft X-rays with a wavelength range of 0.1 to 10 nm and an energy range of 0.12 to 12 keV. Hence, this technique is suitable for agricultural products due to its low penetration and soft nature. Additionally, it can detect

alterations in internal density (Bonnin et al., 2022). This technique exhibits high efficiency in generating X-ray radiographs (Neethirajan et al., 2007), resulting in images of superior clarity and resolution compared to conventional X-ray imaging systems. Computed tomography (CT) is a contemporary advancement in X-ray imaging technology that enables the acquisition of three-dimensional (3D) images. Computed tomography imaging relies on dedicated computer algorithms to reconstruct a 3-D volume or image of an object from multiple projections obtained from various directions (Jiang et al., 2024). One potential drawback of this approach is its high cost and the extended duration required for scanning and processing data Haff and Toyofuku, 2008). Furthermore, the technique presents a three-dimensional object on a two-dimensional detector plane, reducing depth information (Ou et al., 2021). Alterations in grain density resulting from fungal infection form the foundation of X-ray imaging, which can identify mycotoxins due to these changes in grain density. Identifying density variations between healthy and infected kernels can be accomplished by analyzing extracted features from X-ray images (Manickavasagan et al., 2020). This imaging possesses the advantage of exhibiting classification accuracy (Pearson and Wicklow, 2006). Furthermore, in contrast to alternative imaging techniques, it enables non-invasive visualization of the internal characteristics of a specimen, thereby facilitating the identification of concealed flaws or impurities. According to Schoeman et al. (2016), however, this method is associated with limitations such as high cost and the need for time-consuming image analysis procedures.

Figure 15: X-ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) for non-destructive characterisation of food microstructure (Source: Schoeman et al., 2016)

OPPORTUNITIES FOR AFLATOXIN DETECTION USING AI TECHNIQUES

Artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming a thing of the day, and it changes our ways of life every day. AI is modifying every aspect of life, and it is penetrating gradually into research and teaching (online learning). Methods of detecting aflatoxins through AI have recently been noticed, and these methods have become a relief for scientists. The fungi contamination of the feeds can now be checked effectively before it makes its way to the community. AI techniques can perform rapid analysis, process data efficiently, and transmit information effectively. Additionally, they exhibit extensive coverage and high prevalence across the globe. The merits of these methods are listed below:

1. Environmentally friendly – AI methods of detecting aflatoxin are organized methods that do not cause environmental pollution. They are known to be environmentally friendly.
2. Simple preparation – Preparing samples for analysis is straightforward and convenient, as most are non-destructive.
3. Easy function – This method functions digitally and is computed by artificial intelligence. Thereby, it is easy to utilize and function accurately.
4. Good light stability – This AI method with devices like cameras has a sound lighting system, which gives well-illuminated results or output with sharp resonance.

5. Low cost – Recent research has made it easier than ever with smartphones. Some analysis can be done effectively, making it cost-effective and cheaper.
6. Sensitivity – One unique and significant strength of the AI methods is sensitivity, which can be noted across all the AI methods compared to the traditional methods of detecting aflatoxin.
7. Time management – AI methods have shortened the prolonged processing or analysis period. This makes AI methods preferred over traditional ones (Liu et al. 2015).
8. Simultaneous detection – it has been observed that AI methods have the potential to detect multiple mycotoxins at the same time in complex matrices (van Houwelingen et al., 2008).
9. Apart from being sensitive to sample quantification and identification, the AI methods are selective, which directs the methods.
10. Portability - The increasing need for on-site detection of mycotoxins has led to the emergence of portable solutions. Smartphones have presented a groundbreaking opportunity for the detection of mycotoxins on-site, as well as the use of hand-held strip scan readers. These mobile gadgets show quality images in terms of resolution when the images are captured and

processed via an open-source operating system and are equipped with a self-camera and scanner to facilitate rapid inference. Furthermore, (Lei et al., 2014) stated that they enable the wireless transmission of detection outcomes to a tablet computer to store and process data.

11. AI techniques such as UCNPs-based barcoding technology have been found to be effective in obtaining high-resolution images to detect numerous mycotoxins, even with a smartphone. This approach can potentially improve and enhance the speed, accuracy and precision of analysis (Yang 2017).

CHALLENGES OF AI TECHNIQUES

Researchers and institutions, depending on their research data with Artificial Intelligence, might be having challenges in dealing with unexpected hurdles. Some challenges may arise or are coming up because of using AI detectors for aflatoxins and they include:

1.0 Technical know-how

Launching into the AI methods of detecting aflatoxin and getting personnel with the necessary technical know-how skills may be another challenge. This may require regular and time-to-time training of the institution's personnel or recruitment of AI experts for internal development.

2.0 Cost Requirements

From all indications, AI's introduction, usage, development, and integration into analysis and methods of detecting aflatoxin will be expensive. Besides the device's purchase, regular personnel training and software updates require a financial commitment.

3.0 Outdated/Updating challenges.

For Artificial Intelligence systems to function effectively, the devices need to be equipped with adequate infrastructure and processing capabilities and they must be up to date. Meanwhile, it is a common thing or tradition of AI systems to be updated for any development the developer puts in place. Therefore, the systems require regular updates. Any institution that wants to revolutionize its analysis methods with AI must be prepared for the cost and challenges.

4.0 Dependency

Depending on the AI methods, it can be dangerous because the devices used can be faulty or work with the server (internet connectivity), which may sometimes malfunction. We have depended on this

advancement and believe technology can do no wrong. However, AI relies on the data it's given, and if data are incorrectly input, its output decisions will also be faulty. One of the primary challenges in implementing AI is the complexity of the learning process, particularly in translating it into a format that can be effectively integrated into a given system. As stated, the efficacy of specific AI techniques in identifying mycotoxins is contingent upon the type of substrate solution used.

WAY FORWARD

Food is a fundamental aspect of life, and the safety of food is intricately linked to the health and welfare of all living organisms. Therefore, human health has been a concern for decades because of the various emergence of different ailments. Most of these ailments are believed to come from what the body consumes. That is why most countries, institutions, organizations, and individuals pay close attention to the food items for consumption.

One of the paramount and toxic food contaminants is aflatoxins, which is necessary to screen every feed and food item because of the potential damage it can or has caused to the organs of the animals. This is why its detection methods should be reliable and developed, and the developed ones should be very simple, cheap, portable, and accurate detecting methods for the individual concerned.

However, most of these aflatoxin detection methods are specific and can only detect a particular toxin, limiting their scope range. It is pertinent to have or develop strategies that can simultaneously detect more than one aflatoxin or toxin to ensure food safety. Meanwhile, most of these methods are still at the modification stage, with one limitation or another. Therefore, a stable, sensitive, accurate, reduced-cost, and standard reliable device(s) is needed.

The expense of AI technologies and even some older methods is another difficulty, whether for purchase or use. To determine the condition of the food and feed that is readily available at the time, instruments for quick, accurate, and early detection should be made available, particularly to researchers, food companies, and even farmers. Despite the change brought about by the introduction of AI methods, several nations still do not have them, and there are many fewer specific organizations or institutions. As a result, detecting samples as readily and rapidly as feasible in real time has become challenging.

CONCLUSION

Aflatoxins are a significant problem that affects the entire world and has a substantial financial impact on

underdeveloped nations. Although it must be continually checked, contamination can be stopped in the early stages of infection with early and precise detection with adequate methods and techniques. Since aflatoxins cannot be traced, humans and animals should be protected from them. Reduced aflatoxins in crops can be accomplished with a limited number of methods. This review presents such methods and further delves into the power of Artificial intelligence. The continuous progress in technological advancements is expected to mitigate the issue of aflatoxin contamination in both animal feed and human food. The high accuracy of AI tools may be further improved to offer technical support for significantly enhancing the capacity for aflatoxin monitoring and detection in food. In addition, using autonomous technologies enables concurrent processing of numerous samples, reducing the mean processing time for prompt detections.

RECOMMENDATION

- Governments, research institutions, and food and feed industry stakeholders should invest in the development, validation, and large-scale implementation of AI-powered aflatoxin detection technologies.
- Policymakers should create enabling policies and regulatory frameworks that support the adoption of AI-driven aflatoxin monitoring systems, particularly in routine food and feed safety surveillance.
- Strong collaboration should be encouraged among policymakers, food technologists, agricultural researchers, and computer scientists to ensure that AI solutions are scientifically robust, practical, and aligned with food safety needs.
- Personnel involved in food and feed quality control should be adequately trained on the operation, interpretation, and maintenance of AI-based aflatoxin detection tools to ensure reliability and sustainability.

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